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SHORT NOTES / BREVI NOTE

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ESTABLISHED POPULATION OF *ZIZEERIA KARSANDRA* (MOORE, 1865)
(*Lepidoptera Lycaenidae Polyommatainae*) ON THE ISLAND OF LINOSA (PELAGIE, ITALY)

Una popolazione di Zizeeria karsandra (Moore, 1865) (*Lepidoptera Lycaenidae Polyommatainae*) nell'isola di Linosa (Pelagie, Italia)

The distribution of *Zizeeria karsandra* (Moore, 1865) (Lycaenidae Polyommatainae) ranges from Algeria and Lampedusa, eastwards across Libya, Egypt, Israel, Lebanon, Greece, Cyprus and Turkey (HESSELBARTH *et al.*, 1995; MAKRIS, 2003; BAYTA, 2007; BENYAMINI, 2009; PAMPERIS, 2009; VIBORG, 2019). Globally, the species has a significantly wide geographical distribution, ranging from eastern Algeria to the Middle East, extending eastward to tropical Asia and parts of northern and eastern Australia. Within the Mediterranean, in addition to its unbroken distribution from north-eastern Algeria to southern Turkey, it also occurs in Malta, Crete and Cyprus, among other islands (CASSAR *et al.*, 2022). Its close relative, *Zizeeria knysna* (Trimen, 1862), occurs on all of the Canary Islands, the southern segment of the Iberian Peninsula, Morocco and north-western Algeria; it also occurs in France, northwest of the Pyrenees (LERAUT, 2016). *Z. karsandra* was recorded for the first time in the Maltese Islands in 1966, initially identified as *Z. knysna* (SAMMUT, 1982, 1984, 2000), as were all local records until recently (CASSAR, 2018). Subsequently, DNA analysis determined the presence of *Z. karsandra* (VOD *et al.*, 2016; CASSAR, 2018; CASSAR *et al.*, 2022). Over the years, it was observed in a number of localities on Malta, where it appears to have established small, localized populations (CASSAR, 2018). In Italy, it was collected at Capo Lilibeo and in the surroundings of Marsala (western Sicily, Trapani) in August 1952 (BIGOT & STEMPPFER, 1954). Subsequently, the species (reported as *Zizeeria knysna*) was confirmed for the Italian fauna at Lampedusa, at the locality called Guitgia (ROMANO & ROMANO 1995). If the presence at Marsala and the surrounding areas was never re-confirmed, the presence of a stable albeit scarce population of *Z. karsandra* was confirmed at Lampedusa by FIUMI *et al.* (2007). This was subsequently confirmed genetically by CASSAR *et al.* (2022). Beyond the old Sicilian records of 1952 and the more recent records on Lampedusa, documented observations of the species from other parts of Italy were never made, until a small established population was discovered by a group of bird-watchers (MISC) in autumn on the island of Linosa, only 43 km to the north-east of Lampedusa. The number of days spent in the field in the Pelagie Islands, conducting continuous zoological monitoring comprise more than 750, between 2010 to November 2023; most of these days were spent on Linosa. Several specimens of both sexes of *Z. karsandra* were observed in various places at Linosa, regularly each autumn and

spring, with up to 20 per season. Most observations were confirmed within the small private gardens in the town, chiefly the cultivated patches north-west of the cemetery, with several other observations along the coast at a locality called “Mannarazza” and in the cultivated gardens along the Via Mannarazza (Fig. 1). Less individuals were observed in the east/north-eastern parts of the island (between Monte Calcarella and Contrada Faraglioni), but this is an area that was monitored the least, compared to other localities. This butterfly is so inconspicuous, both in terms of dimension and coloration; for these reasons, it is expected that the number of individuals on the island is higher, and it is also probable that the species was present on Linosa before 2010, when it was first observed, but was overlooked. However, it appears to be scarcer on Linosa, when compared to Lampedusa, where it is not uncommon to see individuals in several different localities (e.g.: between Albero Sole and Punta Ponente or at Punta Sottile or along Via Cala Creta) both in late spring and until the end of November.

Fig. 1 — *Zizeeria karsandra* observed on the Linosa island (Foto: O. Janni).

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